

Paper 18**A STUDY ON PROBLEMS FACING BY THE
GOVERNMENT COLLEGE STUDENTS IN RURAL
AREAS - SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KUNDAPUR
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Abstract:

Education to all is a global slogan of Government. Education is one of the most significant factors for development of the economy. It provides an opportunity to reflect on the social, cultural, economy and moral values in the society and also provides brightness to human life it is regarded as potential investment in future for individuals , government also takes initiatives to the development of higher education system of India. Students all over world face a number of problems which dishearten them.

The purpose of the study is examine to understand the distinctive problems and challenges faced by rural government college students in Udupi district , the objective of the study to know how government college are helping rural students in education. To find the problems and challenges of government college students and also identify the satisfactory level of students. The study is mainly based on primary data and collected through questionnaire form. The researcher collected the data from four government colleges in Udupi district.

Keywords: Challenges, Government colleges, satisfactory level, educational facility, rural community.

1. Introduction:

Education plays the most important role in societal development. Rural education implies both the economic betterment of people as well as greater social transformation. Education is a dynamic process that starts from birth. The barrier that the students from rural government to consider that some families don't have the ability to support their child through education process, which means rural student cannot obtain higher education in rural areas. Majority of the population in India still lives in villages and so the topic of rural education in India is of utmost importance.

The foundation to turn India into a strong nation has to be laid down at primary and rural levels and so the quality of education right from the beginning should be excellent. There are plenty of problems which the students face in the rural areas. Only government colleges are there but when you compare the quality of the education in a private and semi government colleges, the difference seems to be higher. The facility of using computers and

internet in the colleges of rural areas can help them a lot to improve the level of the study. Through internet the students will be able to acquire more knowledge and at the same time they will be able to know the outer world in the better way. It is true that the education system of rural areas has been improved a lot in the last 10 years. The government has taken many necessary steps. People have become aware of the necessity of the study. However, still the scope of improving is wide open and both government and common people should try to do that to improve the condition of colleges in rural areas. Rural education is important not only for the enhancement of life quality of the rural community, but also for the overall progress and development of the country.

2. Review of literature:

According to sidoti(2000) access to education in rural and remote areas is a human rights issue.

According to pennington Williams and karvonen,(2006) community colleges located in rural geographical regions also attempts to preserve their local rural culture.

According to a research study conducted by Susan Elkin in (2014), many rural students are academically, socially and culturally under prepared to initially handle college life at urban universities. Rural students often have limited resources including insufficient high school level courses. Rural students’ families may have had little time or resources for academic, socio-cultural challenges compared to urban students when moving into urban universities.

3. Objectives:

1. To understand the problems of rural government college students in kundapura taluk.
2. To understand the educational and basic facilities of the college.
3. To know the effective utilisation of scholarship by the government college students.

4. Research Methodology:

This paper is based on 50 students belongs to rural government degree colleges in kundapura taluk, udupi district. This study purely consists of primary data; it includes government colleges like koteswara SKVMS Govt. First Grade College, Byndoor Govt. First Grade College, Barkur Govt. First Grade College. The questionnaire collected from each college is approximately 13. The analysis done for the study is simple average method and their respective charts.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table No.1

Completion of PUC- education

	Out of 100%
Government	63
Private	37

Chart no.2:
Pie chart showing completion of PUC education

Interpretation:

From the above table shows 63% of the students finished their PUC in government colleges and remaining 37% of the students are from private colleges. From this analysis, majority of the students are from government colleges.

Table no.2:
Basis of selection of degree college by the students

	Out of 100%
Nearby home	20
More facility	40
Referred_by friends	35
None of the above	5

Chart no.2:
Pie chart showing selection of degree college by the students.

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, 40% of students selected this college because they get more facilities, 35% of the students are referred by friends and 20% of the students selected this college because it is nearer to their home and only 5% students selected this college for no reason.

Table 3:

Distance from home to college

	Out of 100%
Below 1 km	12
1-5 km	15
5-10 km	28
More than 10 km	45

Chart no.3:

Pie chart showing distance from home to college

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, 45% of the students come from more than 10km, 28% of the students are coming from 5-10km, 15% from 1-5km and 12% of the students come from below 1km. In this we can interpret that majority of the students come to college from far away places.

Table no.4:

Educational facilities from the college

	Out of 100%
Library	58

Computer lab	27
Internet facility	15
None of the above	00

Chart no.4:

Column chart showing educational facilities from the college

Interpretation:

From the above chart shows, 58% of the college has library facilities, 27 % college has internet facilities, and 15% of the college has computer facilities. This analysis shows that in Government College most of the students are more benefited from the library.

Table no.5:

Basic facilities from the college

	Out of 100%
Rest room	50
Canteen	17
Clean toilets	20
Purified drinking water	13

Chart no.5:

chart showing basic facilities from the college

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, 50% of the college has rest room facilities for students and 20% of the college has clean toilets, 17% has canteen facilities and remaining 13% of the college has purified drinking water.

**Table no.6:
Utilization of scholarship amount**

	Out of 100%
Purchasing books	45
Household expenses	25
Payment of fees	20
Personal use	10

Chart no.6:

Pie chart shows the utilisation of scholarship by the students

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, 45% of the students utilize their scholarship amount for purchasing book, 25% students use it for personal use, 10% uses their scholarship amount for household expenses and 20% of the student utilizes their amount for payment of fees.

Table no.7

Types of teaching method used in college

	Out of 100%
Talk and chalk	40
PPT	25
Seminar/assignments	25
Dictating notes	10

Chart no.7:

Bar chart showing types of teaching method used in college

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, 40% of the college uses talk & chalk method, 10% of the colleges dictating the notes and remaining 25% of the college uses PPT and seminar or assignments.

Table no.8:

Satisfaction level of the students about their college

	Out of 100%
Yes	100
No	0

Chart no.8:

Column chart showing satisfaction level of the students about their college

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, all the 100% students are satisfied about their college. None of the students are unsatisfied.

Findings :

This study respondents are completed their PUC in government colleges and the respondents are selected in government colleges, if they get more facilities from government colleges.

Most of the government college students are coming from very far places (more than 10km) this is the main problem by the government college students because there is no transportation facilities from home to college.

Library plays an important role for government college students other than computer lab, internet. According to basic facilities provided by the college to the students is 50% students are satisfied with rest rooms other than canteen, toilets, drinking water facilities.

Monetary benefits are also given by the college students by the way of scholarships. From the analysis we understood that 65% of students (purchasing of books and payment of fees) so, 65% of students are utilizing their scholarship in an effective purpose. 35% of students are not utilizing for the purpose of education they are utilizing for household expenses and personal use. The government should create awareness to the students for proper utilization of scholarships.

In the government colleges most of the teaching aids are chalk and talk method (40%) 25% of teaching aid is using PPT and 10% only says dictating the notes.

Suggestion :

There are many prominent crises that are holding back rural education to match up with the education system in urban educational centres. The right reformation can definitely bring about a positive change towards the development of rural education.

Indian education system has to improve a lot through creating awareness among students about the importance of education and their social responsibility. Government has to take measures to develop the education system like quality teaching, research and development,

technological development and solving the problems of rural students by providing basic facilities.

References:

1. Journal of research in rural studies
2. Journal of research in rural education
3. www.rural.nic.in
4. www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/rural-education.
5. Arnold, M.L NEWMAN, H.H, Gaddy, B., and Dean, C.B(2005). A look at the condition of rural education research.
6. Malassie, L.(1996): economic development and the programming of rural education.
7. Mosley, malcom(2003) rural development: principles and practice.
8. Van Assche, kristof and hornidge, Anna-katharina(2015) rural development knowledge and expertise in governance.
9. Robinson, E, Amburgey,R, swank, E., and Faulkner, C,(2014), test cheating in rural college.
10. Lehman U, dieleman M, Martineau T. Staffing rural areas in middle and low income countries.
11. Wright JS, Jablonowski AR. The rural distribution of health profession in Georgia.